

CONSULTING SERVICES AS AN IMPORTANT AND MAIN FACTOR IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation

In this article, we can see that the most important changes in the market of services are associated with changes in demand for consulting services, the growing demand for them. In the practice of countries around the world, consulting services are becoming an important factor for the effective operation and development of business entities in a market economy.

Keywords: economics, consulting services, integration, innovation

Sustainable development of the economy of the Republic, its economic and social development, cultural and educational renewal, management of the economy and production in market conditions, the use of consulting services as one of the important and key factors in the production process and development of market economy.

Demand for services in the development of integrated management systems, the introduction of new financial technologies, the development of business evaluation and marketing research is growing. At the same time, the client is interested in a comprehensive solution to the development and implementation of business projects. It is the consulting service that has helped to improve the theoretical and methodological framework for the formation, development of small and medium-sized businesses through the introduction of new innovative ideas.

In world practice, the standard of living of the country's population is determined by the combination of a number of important factors, the scope of the service sector, its share in key macroeconomic indicators, the volume of services per capita. The service sector has a great positive impact on the economy of a particular state and directly contributes to the increase in living standards of the population. Consequently, in developed countries, the share of the industry in GDP is 74%, total employment is 70-75% and the structure of total enterprises is 90-95%.

The interdependence of economic mechanisms corresponding to the modern level of development of the service market requires the relevance of all services.

Most of the services market has a whole network of national consulting firms that have in some sense “regular” clients. However, the demand for their services is still insufficient. This proves that this field in the country is poorly studied theoretically and practically.

In developed countries, however, the growing demand for consulting services has led small firms to become companies that provide a wide range of services. The expansion of the services provided by these companies, the increase in the level of quality has allowed them to merge into larger associations. Consulting services are related to the formation and operation of the market. In particular, the issues of improving the institutional means of state and interdisciplinary relations, increasing the professional activity of enterprises are very relevant.

At present, in the period of rapid development of the economy of our country and its integration into the world economy, the entrepreneurs of the republic face a number of tasks. Based on the experience of strong industrialized countries, it is necessary to study in depth the experience of consulting services of Eastern and Western countries in economic analysis and enterprise management and use it at the level of world requirements.

The creation, development and improvement of market infrastructure, which is an important aspect of the living standards of the population, testifies to the rapid growth of this economy. To this end, one of the urgent issues is to study the economic nature of the market infrastructure of the Republic, to reveal its potential as a factor of development, to implement measures for the comprehensive development of its components.

It is one of the next significant steps, leading to the noble goals of building a free and prosperous life for our country. To fully achieve this goal, we have a number of tasks ahead of us. In this regard, the head of our state Mirziyoyev Sh.M.: “... Analyzing the steady progress of our country on the path of sustainable development, we have every reason to say that over the past years we have taken decisive steps to implement fundamentally important reforms. The main goal of these reforms is to ensure a decent standard of living and quality of life for the population. This policy of rapid and sustainable development will continue unconditionally.”

However, despite the significant involvement of consulting services in the context of economic modernization, tools for their evaluation have not been developed, and there is no reliable methodology for calculating social and economic efficiency. The issues of rational organization of the market of

consulting services, improvement of the mechanism of interaction of its participants should be addressed.

Based on the above, it should be noted that the subject of this dissertation is the study of the stages of formation of the market of consulting services in the Republic, the theoretical basis of the concept of consulting and further improvement of mechanisms and ways of their implementation.

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